

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XVII. Synthesis and Screening of New 3-methyl-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles

(LATE) C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA
Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007.

Manuscript received 31 August 1976, revised 19 November 1976; accepted 14 February 1977.

1-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones have been condensed with different carbonyl reagents to give 3-methyl-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles. These compounds were screened *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* for their antibacterial properties.

THE synthesis and antibacterial properties of some pyrazole derivatives have been described earlier¹⁻⁷ and in continuation of this work, we report here the synthesis of some pyrazoles having the chlorine atom and methyl group in the phenyl ring attached at position-5, with a view to study the effect of these two substituents and compare the results when the phenyl ring is substituted by either of these two.

This paper describes the synthesis of 3-methyl-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles (type I) which were prepared by condensing 1-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with hydrazinehydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and thiosemicarbazide. The purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were checked by TLC and elemental analysis.

All these azoles were later subjected to antibacterial tests *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by the cup-plate agar diffusion method.

Experimental

2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones were synthesised by coupling a number of diazotised sulphonamide bases with 1-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-3-methyl propane-1, 3-dione at 0-5° by the method reported earlier.⁸

Synthesis of 3-methyl-5-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles.

To a solution of 2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-dione (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid was added hydrazine hydrate (100%; 0.05 g) and the reaction mixture refluxed in an oil bath at 160-70° for 5-6 hrs and then left overnight. The deposited solid was filtered, dried and then crystallised from ethanol-glacial acetic acid or ethanol-DMF mixture. In some cases the pyrazole derivatives were obtained by adding water to the reaction mixture.

The reactions with phenylhydrazine and thiosemicarbazide were carried out by the methods already reported.

The results of screening indicate that these compounds exhibit mixed activity. On comparison with the results obtained with the compounds having a chlorine atom in the phenyl ring⁹ attached at position-5, it is clear that the introduction of a methyl group at the ortho position to the chlorine atom causes a decrease in activity against *S. aureus*, but the activity against *E. coli* increases, to a smaller extent. Again, compounds having 5-methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl moiety were found to be most active against *S. aureus*.

All the synthesised products and the results of screening are given in the Tables 1-3.

TABLE—1. 3-METHYL-5-(4'-CHLORO-3'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

($R_1 = H$)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	H	265	72
2.	Acetyl	263	70
3.	Phenyl	240	71
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	265	72
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	236	73
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	230	79
7.	Guanidyl	238	75
8.	α -Pyridyl	258	78
9.	Pyrimidyl	286	78
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	250	75
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	250	74
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	222	77
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	280	78
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	265	73

All compounds were orange in colour

Antibacterial activity. *S. aureus* : Compounds 10, 12, 14 (+); 13 (++++).
E. coli : Comps. 4,5,6,11,13,14(+)

TABLE—2. 1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-5-(4'-CHLORO-3'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

($R_1 = \text{Phenyl}$)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	H	265	73
2.	Acetyl	262	70
3.	Phenyl	210	75
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	241	74
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	190	76
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	187	79
7.	Guanidyl	226	75
8.	α -Pyridyl	245	79
9.	Pyrimidyl	224	78
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	175	75
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	220	74
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	210	73
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	238	75
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	262	74

Compounds : 1, 2, 11, 14 (Orange); 3, 4, 7, 12 (Yellowish orange); 8, 9 (Red); 10, 13 (Orange red); 5 (Yellow).

Antibacterial activity : *S. aureus* : Compounds 5, 7, 11, 12, 14(+); 13 (++++).

E. coli : Compounds 1, 3, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13(+).

TABLE—3. 1-THIOCARBAMIDO-3-METHYL-5-(4'-CHLORO-3'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

($R_1 = \text{thiocarbamido}$)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	H	266	70
2.	Acetyl	265	73
3.	Phenyl	238	75
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	260	70
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	228	73
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	225	74
7.	Guanidyl	245	76
8.	α -Pyridyl	268	76
9.	Pyrimidyl	286	79
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	208	73
11.	2, 6 Dimethylpyrimidyl	205	75
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	250	77
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	282	79
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	266	76

Compounds : 1 to 4 & 6 to 9 (Orange); 5, 10, 13, 14 (Yellow); 11, 12 (Orange yellow).

Antibacterial activity : *S. aureus* : Compounds 6, 7, 10, 12(+); 11(++++); 13(++++)

E. coli : Comps. 2, 3, 6, 7, 12, 13, 14(+); 1(++)

There was good agreement between percentages of carbon and hydrogen found and required.

References

- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 351; 1975, 52, 960.
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 985; 1976, 53, 163.
- A. KABRA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 989.
- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, 37, 147.
- A. KABRA, H. C. MUTREJA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Def. Sci. J.*, 1976, 26, 75.
- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 626.
- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Microbiology*, 1975, 15, 176.
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Def. Sci. J.*, 1975, 25, 55.